

Language and Instructional Methodology CLIL in Pharmacy Universities

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Introduction: Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) has certainly attracted a lot of attention among educators and practitioners in Europe and around the world during the last two decades. This results in a reasonably quick progress toward a theoretical and practice-oriented paradigm for CLIL implementation (Coyle, 2015). According to recent sources, this present instructional technique has been implemented into the school systems of more than 40 European countries at various educational levels. The status of English in Asian countries may play critical roles in the globalized world, such as teaching English to accelerate national growth, learning other cultures, and teaching English as a medium of international communication (Chang, 2011).

Furthermore, the rise of English as a Lingua Franca (henceforth ELF) has progressively influenced English education policies and practices in many Asian nations (Kirkpatrick, 2012). ELF has become a popular form of pluralistic communication among persons of many linguistic backgrounds. Because of these factors, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is a recent pedagogical paradigm that frequently comes up in ELF discussions.

Purpose of the study: Despite the dual focus of CLIL on content and language, as observed by Fortanet-Gómez (2010: 259-260), university content subjects in English are typically taught by content teachers who focus first and foremost on fulfilling the targets established for their subjects. Even if their L2 competency is enough, they may lack the expertise and experience in foreign language education to contribute to their students' language development and proficiency. It is critical for content teachers to understand that integrating English does not simply involve translating their lessons into English, but rather "a combination of the methods used in teaching both the content and the language" (Fortanet-Gómez 2010: 261). Going beyond a subject-focused attitude, as well as the aforementioned openness and flexibility in CLIL, is required of both content and

language teachers (Coyle et al. 2010, Mehisto 2008, Mehisto et al. 2008). Teaching approaches differ throughout university subjects, and language teachers are unfamiliar with them. Students and teachers of content disciplines are typically non-native English speakers, so language-focused courses are crucial since teachers engaging in CLIL projects are primarily concerned with their own fluency in the needed language and may not feel well prepared for the project. However, the success of CLIL is not solely dependent on the level of language proficiency of the teachers (Pavón and Rubio 2010: 51). Furthermore, the levels of the L2 among a particular group of pupils may vary, creating an extra challenge for a non-language teacher. To overcome the problems in supporting language learning by subject teachers and the absence of content understanding by language instructors, CLIL implementation should account for the time teachers require for collaboration. According to Fortanet-Gómez (2010: 273), all teacher training and collaboration activities inside a specific institution should be part of a global institutional strategy with clear objectives and acknowledgement of the parties engaged. Some European universities provide CLIL lecturers with teacher-training courses, which are usually delivered by language departments (for example, Airey 2011, Fortanet-Gómez 2010, Klaassen 2008), or they base their courses taught in English on close collaboration between content and language lecturers (for example, Bruton and Woniak 2013, Zegers 2008).

Materials and methods: All CLIL tasks and activities are based on actual materials carefully selected by content teachers. Because the bulk of publications in natural sciences are in English (Hamel 2007, Ahumada 2011), pharmacy professors do not require any support in this regard. They do, however, occasionally in what refers to constructing a task and measuring the level of language abilities required from pupils to complete the assignment based on a text or a video, typically a very specialized one. When language learning assistance is required, we teach the class jointly as 'team teachers' in some circumstances. The degree programme establishes the workload, learning outcomes, and assessment categories for this course from the top down and is formally approved by the national body for evaluation and accreditation. As a result, the course must be designed with these parameters in mind, but they also provide us ample leeway to construct it in a way that best meets the needs of our students and content instructors. The four practical language skills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking) within the domain of pharmacy and

healthcare can be summarized as the desired learning outcomes. Given the dispersion of CLIL activities in content topics, we chose to divide the course into two halves that mirror content acquisition through English outside of the language. The second portion of the course is devoted to pharmacological treatment, which is tailored to first-year students' limited content knowledge. The ESP course is thus divided into eight short blocks that cover the two major areas of chemistry and pharmaceutical care: Introduction to Pharmacy, Lab Safety, Chemistry, Experiments, Herbal Medicine, Drugs and Medicines, Illness and Disease, and Pharmaceutical Care. Given the course's personalized character, commercial teaching materials are barely appropriate, but not discarded. Individual and group work, as well as progress tests and a final exam, are part of the course's evaluation criteria. There are three individual assignments, one of which is completed in writing in class. The other two individual graded assignments are completed outside of class and consist of uploading audio recordings in order to optimize speaking time and evaluate pronunciation. Students complete a pair or group assignment at the end of each of the course's two main parts. Because vocabulary development is an integral aspect of any language learning process, knowledge and application of technical specialist vocabulary is one of the primary focuses of ESP. Learners are expected to employ specialized vocabulary for effective communication with others within a specific field of study or professional activity. Not unexpectedly, our students responded that specialist vocabulary in the field of pharmacy was their key anticipation for this ESP course. Vocabulary exercises are interwoven throughout the course to develop students' receptive and productive vocabulary, or words that learners know and comprehend when they meet them in reading or writing. A significant amount of technical vocabulary in English includes terms of Graeco-Latin origin, which are easily recognized in written texts by fluent Spanish speakers, making their receptive goals in scientific English relatively easier. However, specialized vocabulary also includes seemingly regular vocabulary used in everyday language that takes on specific meanings when used in a certain academic or professional setting, such as the verb dissolve. The use of English across subjects may also result in various words being used by different instructors, which may lead to misunderstandings and confusion. As a result, our consultations with content lecturers also assist to unify terminology and prepare how to resolve variances appropriately.

Conclusion:

In this article, we demonstrated that a language-focused ESP course is still required in a CLIL setting, primarily to raise students' awareness of language and its role in disciplinary communication, as well as to provide students with the necessary vocabulary, structures, and learning strategies to complete their disciplinary tasks in English.

The end product of our course design is diverse, based on exercises and concentrated activities that some may regard as too traditional, conservative, and form-oriented, but it embodies a balance between disciplinary language and substance. Our materials and activities are linked to other activities conducted in English in other Pharmacy topics, therefore ESP and CLIL aim to complement one other to encourage meaningful learning. In this article, we will demonstrate that a language-focused ESP course is still required in a CLIL setting, primarily to raise students' awareness of language and its role in disciplinary communication, as well as to provide students with the necessary vocabulary, structures, and learning strategies to complete their disciplinary tasks in English.

The end product of our course design is diverse, based on exercises and concentrated activities that some may regard as too traditional, conservative, and form-oriented, but it embodies a balance between disciplinary language and substance. Our materials and activities are linked to other activities conducted in English in other Pharmacy topics, therefore ESP and CLIL aim to complement one other to encourage meaningful learning.

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